

GEOMETRICAL STABILITY OF CFRP LAMINATE CONSIDERING PLY ANGLE MISALIGNMENT

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Abstract

Accurate geometrical stability is required for the precise structures like telescopes. It was reported that symmetrical CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics) laminates show unpredictable deformation due to the ply angle misalignment and temperature change. This ply angle misalignment is unavoidable. One of the answer to mitigate the deformation due to the ply angle misalignment is to chose effective stacking sequence. We discussed here the effective stacking sequence to reduce the thermal deformation.

1 Introduction

Since CFRP has excellent thermal stability in addition to high specific stiffness and strength, it can be used as the main material for precise structures like telescopes^[1]. The main mirror can be made larger than conventional mirrors by using CFRP, which can drastically improve the resolution of the telescope. The main mirror requires accurate dimensional stability for long-term. For instance, a mirror of 3.5m diameter must keep its surface-geometry deviation within 5 μm RMS (root mean square)^[2]. In general, the P-V (Peak to Valley) value of reflecting mirror must be kept within $\lambda/8$. λ means the wave length of interest. $\lambda/8$ is named Rayleigh limit. If the mirror deforms more than the value of Reyleigh limits, the resolution of reflective mirror decreases. Therefore, geometrical stability in CFRP laminates is critical problem for using CFRP to precise structures.

CFRP mirrors have been developed by lots of researchers^{[3]-[7]}. The smooth mirror surface can be created by transcription and polishing techniques. However, the unpredictable deformation with the temperature change is unsolved problems. To reduce

the out-of-plane deformation, symmetric stacking sequence is usually adopted. The problem is that there is no ideal symmetric laminate. This is because ply angle misalignment is inevitable when we stacked ply. The symmetrical laminates are specifically asymmetric. Laminates show not only the in-plane deformation but also show out-of-plane deformation with the temperature change. Author et al. found that a standard deviation of approximately 0.4° of ply angle misalignment exists when A person who is an expert at fabricating laminates stacks ply by a hand tape placement method^[8]. In order to make good use of CFRP, it is important to discuss the proper stacking sequence of CFRP laminate that mitigate the effect of ply angle misalignment on the deformation.

In this research, we discuss the effects of stacking sequence on the thermal deformation of CFRP laminate considering ply angle misalignment. The analysis including laminate theory, Monte Carlo method and Mohr's curvature circle was performed

2 Analytical procedure

2.1 Laminate theory

Thermal deformation of laminate can be calculated by the classical laminate theory. The main equation is as follows;

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} N_x^T \\ N_y^T \\ N_{xy}^T \\ M_x^T \\ M_y^T \\ M_{xt}^T \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

A_{ij} , B_{ij} , and D_{ij} are the laminate extensional stiffness, coupling stiffness, and laminate bending stiffness,

respectively. N^T and M^T mean hygrothermal force due to the temperature change and the resultant moments per unit length. N^T and M^T are given by

$$\{N^T\} = \sum_{k=1}^n [T]_k^{-1} [Q_{ij}]_k \{\alpha\} \Delta T (z_k - z_{k-1}) \quad (2)$$

$$\{M^T\} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n [T]_k^{-1} [Q_{ij}]_k \{\alpha\} \Delta T (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2) \quad (3)$$

See reference [9] to understand detail descriptions for laminate theory. In this analysis, matrix B_{ij} is an important parameter. It is obvious according to equation (1) that the curvature κ occurs with axial force N^T if B_{ij} matrix is not zero. It means that the out-of-plane deformation occurs by temperature change or moisture absorption. In the case of ideally symmetric laminate, B_{ij} matrix becomes zero. However, the laminates have some ply angle misalignment, and B_{ij} matrix is practically not zero. The curvature κ occurred by temperature change can be calculated using equation (1).

2.2 Mohr's circle of curvature

From equation (1), curvatures κ_x , κ_y , κ_{xy} can be obtained. In general, dimensional stability of mirror is evaluated by P-V value. We introduce the procedure to determine P-V value using each curvatures. In order to determine the P-V value, main curvatures κ_1 and κ_2 should be calculated from κ_x , κ_y and κ_{xy} . Based on the main curvatures, we can easily determine the P-V value. Hyer proposed the procedure to calculate the main curvatures using Mohr's circle of curvature^[10]. Mohr's circle of curvature is the same concept with the Mohr's strain circle. Fig. 2 is the concept of mohr's circle of curvature. Horizontal axis is a bending curvature κ_b and vertical axis is a twisted curvature κ_{tw} . The center point of the circle is always on the horizontal axis, and the coordinate of the center circle is described as follow:

$$C = \frac{\kappa_x + \kappa_y}{2} \quad (4)$$

Radius of circle can be written as

$$R = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\kappa_x - \kappa_y}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\kappa_{xy}}{2}\right)^2} \quad (5)$$

Main curvature κ_1 and κ_2 are,

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_1 &= R + C \\ \kappa_2 &= R - C \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The relationship between curvature radius and height is given by

$$\rho = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{c^2}{4h} + h \right) \quad (7)$$

Each letter definitions are shown in Fig. 3. c denotes length in horizontal direction and curvature can be obtained as a reciprocal number of curvature radius. If the height in equation (7) is extremely small, the second term of right side becomes negligible, and curvature radius is in inverse proportion to the height. In other word, curvature is proportional with the height. In the case of asymmetric laminates and infinitesimal deformation, κ_1 and κ_2 show opposite sign each other. So h_1 and h_2 become opposite sign. P-V value h_{pv} is written as

$$h_{pv} = h_1 - h_2 \quad (8)$$

Here κ_{pv} is described as follow:

$$\kappa_{pv} = \kappa_1 - \kappa_2 = 2R \quad (9)$$

We can evaluate the P-V value of the laminate with circle form by using equation (4)-(9).

Fig. 2 Mohr's circle of curvature

2.3 Monte Carlo Method

The Monte Carlo method is a statistical analysis technique for obtaining approximate values by iterating the calculation using random numbers. The solution for an unsolvable problem can be

approximated by performing a sufficient number of iterations. In this analysis, random numbers based on the normal distribution were given as ply angle misalignments. The probability density function is defined as follows:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}s} \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2s^2}\right) \quad (10)$$

where μ is the mean value and s is the standard deviation. In this analysis, the mean value is 0, and s was assumed to be 0.4° . This value is determined based on the previous research^[8]. This statistical meaning is that the random number within $\pm 0.4^\circ$ will be chosen approximately 68% and the numbers within $\pm 0.8^\circ$ will be abstracted approximately 95%. The probability to choose above 1° of ply angle misalignment is extremely low. This ply angle misalignment is the value when a person who is an expert at fabricating laminates cut the prepreg tapes and stacked them carefully. Precise structures are usually made by a hand tape placement and autoclave method to fabricate high quality CFRP laminates.

First, the random numbers were generated and they were added to each layer. In the case of 24 ply laminates, 24 random numbers were chosen based on the normal distribution, and added to each layer. From each ply angle, thermal deformation can be calculated by classical laminate theory in equation (1). Using equation (1) – (9), κ_{pv} can be determined. In this analysis, we repeated the analysis up to 10,000 times. The mean value of κ_{pv} can be obtained as follows:

$$\kappa_{pv, \text{mean}} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N \kappa_{pv,i}^2}}{N} \quad (11)$$

where N is the number of repetitions, i.e. 10,000 in this analysis. The commercial matrix manipulation program Matlab 2007a was used in this analysis.

2.4 Mechanical properties of materials

Pitch based high-elasticity carbon fiber is usually adopted to the dimensional stable structure. Therefore, prepreg tapes made of pitch-based high-elasticity carbon fiber (K63712, Mitsubishi Chemical) and thermosetting epoxy resin (AY33, Mitsubishi Chemical) was prepared. Unidirectional

laminates were fabricated by an autoclave method. Mechanical properties of the laminates in fiber, transverse, and $\pm 45^\circ$ directions were examined based on JIS K7073. CTEs (Coefficient of Thermal Expansions) in the fiber and transverse direction were also obtained by using a thermomechanical analyzer (Thermoplus TMA8230, Rigaku). Table 1 shows the mechanical properties of unidirectional laminates. Subscript 1 denotes the fiber direction and subscript 2 means transverse direction. Fig. 5 is the experimental results for CTEs. CTE in fiber directions showed negative values, on the other hand, CTE in transverse direction exhibited considerable large values compared to the CTE in fiber direction. The negative CTE in fiber direction is due to the negative CTE of high-elasticity carbon fiber. CTE in transverse direction slightly varied with temperature. In this analysis, we assumed CTE is a constant value as shown in Table 1. Thickness of the laminate strongly affects κ_{pv} . If the thickness of the laminate increases, bending stiffness of the laminate increases. As a result, the deformation of the laminate decreases. In order to focus an effect of stacking sequence against the thermal deformation, we assumed that the thickness of the laminate is a constant value of 2.4mm. Because of this assumption, increasing the total number of layers corresponds to using thinner layers.

3. Analytical result

3.1 Effect of ply angle

We can choose the ply angle of the laminates arbitrarily. However, in light of practical use, rotation angles of each layer are 30° , 45° , 60° or 90° , respectively. In these common stacking sequences, the most effective stacking sequence to reduce out-of-plane deformation is discussed. Thickness of the laminates and total number of plies affect the thermal deformation. Therefore, they were assumed to be 2.4mm and 24 plies, respectively.

Fig. 4 is an effect of stacking angle against the thermal deformation. $\kappa_{pv, \text{means}}$ was calculated when the temperature of laminates varies 1K. It was found that the thermal deformation of cross-ply laminate $[0/90]_6$ was larger than other quasi-isotropic laminates. Large twisted deformation (κ_{xy}) was observed for the cross-ply laminates, because they do not include the fibers in $\pm 45^\circ$ direction. As a result, κ_{pv} for cross-ply laminates exhibited larger deformation compared

to the other stacking sequence. It was reported that CFRP cross-ply laminates that have the dimension of 300 x 300 x 2.3 mm showed the out-of-plane deformation about 300-800 μm by absorbing water^[8]. Quasi-isotropic laminates with the same material and geometry of above laminate deformed approximately 60-80 μm by moisture absorption^[11]. The difference of deformation for cross-ply laminates and quasi-isotropic laminates was approximately 10 times. The analytical results corresponded to the experimental tendency. The difference of thermal deformation for $[0/60/120]_{4s}$, $[-45/0/45/90]_{3s}$ and $[0/30/60/90/120/150]_{2s}$ was quite small.

3.2 Effect of total ply number

In order to discuss the effect of total ply number against the thermal deformation, thermal deformation analysis was performed with various total ply number. As mentioned above, the thickness of the laminate was a constant value of 2.4mm. and increasing ply number correspond to the use of thinner layer. Fig. 5 shows the effect of total ply number against the thermal deformation. When the number of repeat n is 1, large deformation was observed for all stacking sequence. However, if the number of repeat n became 2, the amount of deformation decreased less than half. The effect of ply angle misalignment might be reduced by increasing total ply number. This effects reduces the thermal deformation of the laminates. It is worth noting that increasing ply number becomes modest

effect for thermal deformation when total ply number is more than 24ply. For example, in the case of $[-45/0/45/90]_{ns}$, the deformation decreased from $5.12 \times 10^{-8} \text{mm}^{-1}$ to $1.97 \times 10^{-8} \text{mm}^{-1}$ (approximately 60% reduction) when the ply number varied from 8ply to 16ply. On the other hand, the deformation decreased $15.7 \times 10^{-9} \text{mm}^{-1}$ from to $13.5 \times 10^{-9} \text{mm}^{-1}$ (only 14% reduction) when the ply number varied from 24ply to 32ply. Because of the limitation of the thickness and working efficiency, the range of 16ply to 24ply is appropriate ply number for light and precise CFRP plate in the case of $[-45/0/45/90]_{ns}$ laminates. If the total number of ply is more than 24ply, the dependency of stacking sequence on thermal deformation was extremely small. Meanwhile, the thermal deformation depends on the stacking sequence of laminate if the total ply number is less than 16 ply. It was presumed that the stacking sequence is an important factor in case that the total number is few.

Conclusions

Thermal deformation analysis considering ply angle misalignment was performed. The effects of stacking sequence and total ply number against the thermal deformation was discussed. It was found that the cross-ply laminates deformed 10 times larger than quasi-isotropic laminates. This tendency corresponds to the experimental results reported other paper. The effect of ply angle misalignment might be reduced by increasing total ply number. This effects reduces the thermal deformation of the laminates.

Fig. 4 Effect of stacking angle on the thermal deformation

Fig. 5 Effect of ply number against the thermal deformation

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